

MDPI Consortia Gold Open Access Publish Agreement 2025 – 2026 with ZB MED

Parties

Deutsche Zentralbibliothek für Medizin (ZB MED). Informationszentrum Lebenswissenschaften, Gleueler Straße 60 50931 Cologne, Germany, represented by the Management Board,

on behalf of participating members (Annex A) hereinafter “Institution”;

and

MDPI AG, Grosspeteranlage 5, 4052 Basel, Switzerland (hereinafter „MDPI“).

1. Definitions

IOAP

Institutional Open Access Program. A scheme operated by MDPI for the purpose of sharing information with participating institutions.

Manuscript

A piece of research with identified authors submitted to an MDPI journal with the aim of publication as a research paper. All submitted manuscripts containing original research undergo a rigorous peer review process following the norms for research journals.

APC

Article processing charge. A per-article fee that covers the cost of administration of peer review, professional production (including copy-editing, language editing, and preparation of final published versions in PDF, XML, and other formats), journal management (including communication with the editorial board, development of editorial strategy, dissemination of published research), and other tasks necessary to maintain an academic publishing house.

Central payment

A process whereby invoices for APCs are sent to a single recipient based at the Institution for payment rather than individual authors. Invoices related to central payment may be collated and issued on a regular basis (e.g., monthly or quarterly) rather than for each individual manuscript.

Prepayment

Transfer of funds in advance from the Institution to MDPI to cover for APCs. The funds are used to pay for invoices as they are raised and used only with the approval of the Institution.

Susy

MDPI’s online submission system, used to manage the editorial process for manuscripts and handle administration of APCs.

Affiliated authors

Any author of a manuscript who is an employee of or holds a research position at the Institution. This includes university staff, undergraduate and postgraduate students, those on temporary or permanent research contracts, lecturers, and full professors. Those granted an emeritus title are also included. Those with a temporary status (e.g., visiting researchers) qualify as affiliated authors if the research in the manuscript was partially or wholly conducted at the Institution. Affiliated authors must include the Institution address in their affiliation listed on the manuscript and be authorized to do so by the Institution. Affiliated authors are eligible to receive discounts described in this agreement.

2. Purpose and Duration

This document sets out arrangements for how the IOAP operates. This agreement is effective as of 1 January 2025 until 31 December 2026.

The contracting parties shall enter into discussions on a possible extension, renewal or amendment of the contractual conditions no later than two months before the end of the contract.

Institutions may adhere to the agreement until the end of Q2 of 2025. Participating institutions in options 1 and 3 may change their funding option during the contract term. When joining or switching to Option 2 in 2025 or 2026, the flat fee shall be calculated on a pro rata basis.

3. Program Description

MDPI will grant the Institutions access to a dedicated account on Susy where they will be able to view manuscripts and associated metadata. In the case of central payment, APCs, eligible authors, and invoices will also be accessible.

IOAP member institutions are listed on <http://www.mdpi.com/about/ioap>. For clarity and consistency of communication, the Institutions are encouraged to make a public announcement about their participation.

Archiving

The Institution can choose to enable auto-archiving. In this case, all manuscripts published in MDPI journals by authors affiliated with the Institution will be deposited to the institution's internal repository on the issue release date of the journal using the SWORD 1.3 protocol, or an alternative mechanism at the discretion of MDPI.

4. Financial Terms

Authors affiliated with the Institution will receive a discount on the APC for any paper published in an MDPI journal. The IOAP discount may be combined with other discount types. However, please note that only one discount through an IOAP scheme is permitted per paper.

Participating institutions will select between the following three options:

Option 1- Central Payment

MDPI will provide a **30% discount** to the Institution for central coverage where the affiliated author is the corresponding author on the manuscript. For any non-central manuscript, MDPI will grant a **15% discount** on the published APC for the journal.

The discount will be confirmed by MDPI upon submission and the Institution may disavow an author at any time before the acceptance of the manuscript.

MDPI reserves the right to ask the Institution for evidence of affiliated author status before granting a discount.

The Institution has opted into central payment and takes the responsibility of paying invoices for any affiliated authors that identify themselves as the corresponding author on a manuscript.

MDPI does not set the criteria for central payment eligibility but can automatically enroll authors for central payment based on their email address. MDPI can, upon request, enroll authors for central payment based on whether they are identified as a corresponding author.

The Institution will have access to the IOAP Dashboard and shall confirm the author's eligibility upon notification of submission, but no later than 14 working days after the paper's acceptance. The invoice status (central or non-central) at that time shall be deemed accurate and final by MDPI and will not be subject to modification.

Institutions using central payment may choose a prepayment account to pay for APCs. If the institution has agreed to pay an invoice centrally the total will be deducted from the deposited funds.

Option 2 - Flat Fee

The Institution agrees to provide the total fund across the two years which will be allocated as an annual, one-time fee to secure the option for unlimited article publication across any MDPI journals. This arrangement permits an unrestricted number of articles to be published, subject to journal acceptance, with no imposed limits or caps on publication quantity. The funding for the year 2025 shall be paid in full by February 28, 2025. Consequently, the funding for the year 2026 shall be paid in full by February 28, 2026. The institution will also have the option to pay in full for the entire contract duration in a single payment by February 28, 2025.

In practice, this means that any author who identifies themselves as affiliated with the Institution and is listed as the corresponding author of the manuscript will be able to publish their papers at no additional cost.

For tracking purposes, an invoice will still be issued and made available in the dedicated IOAP Dashboard.

The Institution will have continuous and unrestricted access to the IOAP Dashboard, and shall confirm the author's eligibility no later than 14 working days after paper's acceptance. The invoice status (central or non-central) at that time shall be deemed accurate and final by MDPI and shall not be subject to modification.

For any manuscript not eligible for the Flat Fee where at least one author is an affiliated author, MDPI will grant a 15% discount on the published APC for the journal.

Option 3 – Author pays

Authors affiliated with the Institution will receive a 15% discount on the APC for any paper published in an MDPI journal which may be combined with other discount types. A list of current APC charges is available at <http://www.mdpi.com/about/apc>.

Additional Discounts

All affiliated authors also receive a 10% discount on charges associated with open access book publishing with MDPI Books (i.e., book processing charges: BPCs), and a 15% discount on the language editing services provided by MDPI Author Services. The additional discounts are available for every one of the offered options.

5. Invoicing Information

The invoices will be issued by:

*MDPI AG
Grosspeteranlage 5
4052 Basel
Switzerland*

MDPI will notify the Institution in the case of an address change.

MDPI's Swiss bank account details are listed here: <https://www.mdpi.com/about/payment> . We prefer to receive payment in CHF, but also accept payments in EUR. Any taxes, if applicable shall be the sole responsibility of the Institution: <https://www.mdpi.com/about/terms-and-conditions>.

The only valid email address sent from MDPI has the email domain @mdpi.com.

6. Confidentiality

The terms of this document are not confidential.

However, the Institutions must treat with strict confidence any manuscript and associated metadata provided by MDPI, and any details shared about the editorial process.

7. Data protection

The parties must comply with the applicable data protection law, especially the Swiss Data Protection Act ("SDPA"), the General Data Protection Regulation ("GDPR") and all relevant data protection and privacy legislation in other relevant jurisdictions. If applicable, the parties agree to implement a data processing agreement compliant with applicable data protection law.

8. Miscellaneous

Basel, Switzerland shall be the place of jurisdiction for all legal disputes arising of this agreement, even if the Institution has their domicile outside of Switzerland.

Swiss law applicable at the place of jurisdiction of MDPI shall apply exclusively, excluding the conflict of law's provisions, the United Nations Convention on Contracts for the International Sale of Goods of 11 April 1980 ("Vienna Sales Convention") and any other international conventions.

If any provisions of the agreement should be found invalid, this shall not affect the validity of the remaining provisions. In any such case, the contracting parties shall negotiate on the invalid clause to substitute by a valid arrangement as close as possible to the original provision.

Either party may terminate this arrangement if the other party commits a material breach of this Agreement and fails to remedy that breach following written notice by the terminating party, specifying the breach and requiring that it be remedied.

Annexes A-C are an integral part of this agreement:

Annex A – Participants list

Annex B – Product sheet

Annex C – Registration form

For MDPI

For the Consortium

Place, date:

Place, date:

Signature

Alistair Freeland

Signature

Franziska Fischer

Chief Operating Officer

Commercial Director

Signature

Peter Roth

Head of Publishing

MDPI AG

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